

KEY ISSUES OF ORGANIZING INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT ACTIVITY OF THE ENTERPRISE

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Annotation: This article examines the importance of innovation and the features of innovative management. Innovative processes and types are studied. Based on the analysis, recommendations on the use of innovative management are proposed.

Key words: innovative management, innovative processes, innovative management, innovation strategy, innovation.

The large-scale socio-economic reforms being carried out in our republic today require economic entities to improve their management system based on modern mechanisms. This is due, on the one hand, to the need to democratize economic activity and gradually transition to new modern methods of economic management based on the principles of market relations at all levels of management, and on the other hand, it is based on improving the system of state regulation of the entire system of economic relations in accordance with market conditions using economic methods. In the conditions of market relations, it is necessary to foresee urgent problematic issues, changes that are taking place and opportunities that may arise, to develop economic policy and strategy, and to manage these changes using new methods, new techniques and technologies.

One of the means of achieving the goals of the enterprise is an innovative strategy. It is characterized by the ability to influence changes in the internal and external environment of the enterprise. From this point of view, the development of an innovative strategy is a necessary measure when a crisis situation arises in the enterprise. According to A.A. Belyaev and E.M. Korotkov, innovation is a necessary element of anti-crisis management [4].

In the initial approaches, innovation was considered a process associated with creative activity. It was understood as a "black box" that could find expression in an irrational, unorganized model [5]. Over the years, as a result of the development of scientific potential and technology, and the improvement of technological processes, several models of innovation have emerged. These models differ depending on the characteristics of the enterprise and the macroeconomic environment.

According to A.V. Zubkov, innovations are divided into the following types:
– product innovation;

- technological innovation;
- process innovation;
- organizational innovation [3].

Product innovation is related to the creation of new products or the improvement of existing products. It is also carried out in conjunction with technological innovation, since a new product requires new knowledge and technology to produce it.

Process innovation aims to save resources and improve product quality, resulting in increased production capacity.

Organizational innovation is aimed at improving the organizational structure of an enterprise in order to bring it to a new level and achieve efficiency. R. Gimush and F. Matmurodov distinguished the innovation process into 2 types: leading (pioneer) and chasing.

The process of innovation of the pioneer type represents the threshold for achieving world leadership (in the case of the USA).

The process of catch-up innovation is characterized by being cheap and producing results quickly (for example, Japan).

According to J. Kambarov and N. Makhmudova, innovation management consists of the processes of developing innovation projects aimed at implementing the enterprise's established innovation strategy, supporting initiatives, introducing technical and technological innovations, and expanding production through the introduction of innovations in management, planning, motivation, and control.

The use of innovations in enterprise management serves the efficient operation of enterprises. These innovations can include:

- organization of business intelligence (innovative technologies that combine the stability of business operations and the efficiency of all types of enterprise activities in conditions of unlimited data);
- implementation of the concept of business continuity (Business Continuity Management - innovative technologies that effectively affect disruptions in business processes, reduce losses and reduce costs);
- application of a marketing strategy for management (reconstruction of old or creation of new marketing tools, marketing research assets, creation of brand capital).

Innovation management is a set of organizational economic, psychological, social methods, methods of management of all stages of the innovation process.

It is also about implementing changes in management. In our opinion, these processes can be reflected as follows (Fig. 1.)

The technical sphere of management, based on innovation, includes labor tools, equipment and devices, and means of communication. The technological sphere includes technological processes, raw materials, personnel qualifications, know-how, etc. The socio-economic sphere focuses on the organization of labor, creative potential, organizational culture, and supply elements.

Figure 1. Scheme of areas of implementation of innovative management

The management cycle includes factors such as new decision-making methods, organizational structure, employee motivation, and personnel management.

Resources and organizational structures that provide innovative processes can be different. These include technopolises, laboratories of large corporations, organizational forms of exhibition trade complexes, innovation centers, management and organizational consulting firms. These resources are developing as a result of the development of science and technology in the market economy.

Stimulation of innovative activity by the state can be implemented in the following forms:

- direct financing.
- providing interest-free bank loans to innovators;
- creation of innovative funds and giving them benefits;

- reduction of patent payments to individual inventors;
- establishment of technopolis and technoparks;
- allocating targeted subsidies and subsidies to small innovative businesses by the state;
- setting a preferential tax rate for profits from scientific developments;

The innovative potential of an enterprise is one of the characteristics that indicate its competitiveness. At the same time, the innovative capabilities of an enterprise also depend on the conditions created for it by the state, and the state policy in the field of innovation. Therefore, developed countries in their state programs set the goal of developing scientific and technological equipment, innovation, and improving the infrastructure in this area.

In particular, the US has a developed institutional structure in science and technology policy. The American Science Foundation and the American Science Council determine the directions of fundamental research. They also implement the scientific and technical interests of industry and universities. The peculiarity of the American structure in the management of scientific and technological development is reflected in the close interaction of the state with private business [2].

These organizations are financed by public and private sources. Studies conducted in the United States have shown that the money spent gives good results. Technological transfers serve to increase the volume of supply and sales, improve product quality, introduce new equipment and technologies, improve production processes, and improve personnel skills.

The Council for Scientific Affairs describes the strategic direction of the state for scientific and technological development and determines how much money will be spent on them from the state budget. The Science and Technology Administration is engaged in the development and implementation of major national programs. The Japan Research and Development Corporation also operates in this area and supports new scientific firms [1].

In our opinion, it is necessary to form a legal basis for the creation of innovative management in our country. Also, during the implementation of the innovation policy by the state, the following measures should be implemented:

- state support for fundamental research;
- freedom of scientific and technical creativity;
- integration of education, scientific and technical activities;
- support for competition within the framework of innovative activities, creation of a favorable innovative environment;

- development of a strategy for training personnel for new industries;
- development of international cooperation.

In addition, the introduction of new technologies in production, the creation of scientific research centers for the practical application of innovations aimed at increasing product competitiveness and increasing labor productivity will create opportunities for sustainable development of our economy.

The use of innovations in the production process is reflected in the use of innovations in working with partners in the external and internal environment of the enterprise. In particular, it is necessary to pay attention to such factors as the production of products that do not require initial investment in the technological process, the introduction of innovations in working with suppliers, and the saving of time and excess costs.

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